

Esfinge Metadata Code Conventions

FREE AND CLARIFIED CONSENT TERM (FCCT)

You are being invited to participate in the research entitled "Towards Application-specific Code Conventions for Annotation-based Frameworks".

Participation: The experiment is divided in two parts. In the first you will be asked to accomplish two implementation tasks, one using the Esfinge Metadata API, and other using the Java standard reflection API.

The instructions for this part of the experiment can be found on:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1iKvrPvCBHymssJoEauo_qvaJ0hLSOpLeiQvjK47JeBk/edit?usp=sharing

Then, in the second part, you will be asked to answer the questions of this questionnaire.

Confidentiality and anonymity: The information in this research is strictly confidential, and disclosed only in scientific events or publications and will only be used for this purpose, with no identification of the participant(s), unless between those responsible for the study, ensuring full confidentiality about their participation.

Contact information for those responsible for the research: During the research period, you have the right to ask any questions or ask for any other clarification, simply contacting one of the researchers by the e-mail address everaldogjr@gmail.com.

Voluntary Participation: You have the right to refuse to participate in the referred survey or to withdraw from this study, at any time, without prejudice or retaliation, for your voluntary decision. To quit, just leave the site before completing the survey.

Data retention: The data will be kept after the completion of the project for 5 years.

Consent Registration: Once the questionnaire is being carried out using an electronic form, you must check the option in which you affirm that you agree with the participation of the study and make a copy of it after completing it. You can also request a copy of the document signed by the researchers.

*Obrigatório

1. Informed consent *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I consent to participate in this experiment. *Pular para a pergunta 2*
- I do not consent, and hence prefer not to participate
Pular para a seção 6 (We understand you do not wish to participate in the study! :))

Personal Information

In this section you will be asked questions about yourself, experience with software development and code annotations

2. Name *

3. GitHub Username *

4. How well are you familiar with Code Annotations? (Other languages contain similar feature, such as attributes (C#) and decorators (Python). When answering about your experience with code annotations, also consider your familiarity with other similar features and knowledge on metaframeworks.) *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very Familiar

5. What is your primary programming language? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Java
- C#
- C++
- Python
- JavaScript
- Typescript
- C
- Outro: _____

About your tasks using the Esfinge Metadata API

In this section we are interested in your experience while implementing your task using the Esfinge Metadata API.

6. How many tasks you accomplished? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- One
- Two
- None

7. How much time you spent implementing the tasks? *

8. You felt the necessity to interrupt the task for any reason? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

9. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, answer how many interruptions you made

10. Do you think that interruptions affected your total time for completing the tasks?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

11. Select the difficulties that you had while executing these tasks

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Understand the unit tests
- Understanding Esfinge Metadata documentation
- Understand the task that needed to be done
- Understand what the target framework do
- Use the Code Conventions feature from Esfinge Metadata
- Read and navigate in the target framework code
- Implement the conventions feature
- Find where the conventions should be implemented
- Outro: _____

12. Did you needed to search for extra information, besides the provided documentation? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

13. If you answered "yes" to the previous question, tell which material and why you need this extra material

14. Describe your overall experience while implementing the tasks using the Esfinge Metadata API *

About your task using the standard Java reflection API

In this section we are interested in your experience while implementing your task using the standard Java reflection API.

15. How many tasks you accomplished? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- One
- Two
- None

16. How much time you spent implementing this task? *

17. You felt the necessity to interrupt the task for any reason? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

18. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, answer how many interruptions you made

19. Do you think that interruptions affected your total time for completing the task?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

20. Select the difficulties that you had while executing this task

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Understand the unit tests
- Understand the task that needed to be done
- Understand the usage of Reflection in the code
- Understand what the target framework do
- Use Reflection features in the implementation of the Code Conventions
- Read and navigate in the target framework code
- Implement the conventions feature
- Find where the conventions should be implemented
- Outro: _____

21. Did you needed to search for extra information, besides the provided documentation? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

22. If you answered "yes" to the previous question, tell which material and why you need this extra material

23. Describe your overall experience while implementing the task using the Java standard reflection API *

Approaches evaluation

In this section you will present your opinion about both approaches

24. Which you consider advantages of using Esfinge Metadata API for creating Code Conventions comparing to the other approach *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Development speed
- Easy to be implemented
- Resulting code is easy to be changed
- Resulting code is more readable
- Easy to learn
- Outro: _____

25. Which you consider disadvantages of Esfinge Metadata API for creating Code Conventions comparing to the other approach *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Development is hard to be performed
- Development takes more time
- Requires a large learning curve
- Resulting code is more complex
- Resulting code is hard to maintain
- Resulting code has duplicated code
- Outro: _____

26. Which you consider advantages of using standard Java reflection API for creating Code Conventions comparing to the other approach *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Development speed
- Easy to be implemented
- Resulting code is easy to be changed
- Resulting code is more readable
- Easy to learn
- Outro: _____

27. Which you consider disadvantages of standard Java reflection API for creating Code Conventions comparing to the other approach *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Development is hard to be performed
- Development takes more time
- Requires a large learning curve
- Resulting code is more complex
- Resulting code is hard to maintain
- Resulting code has duplicated code
- Outro: _____

28. If you were responsible for a metadata framework and needed to implement code conventions for its annotations, which approach you would use. *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Java Standard Reflection API
- Esfinge Metadata API

29. Justify your previous answer *

We understand you do not wish to participate in the study! :)

Google Formulários